

FINLAND’S EXPERIENCE IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF UZBEKISTAN'S EDUCATION SYSTEM

**¹Toirov Shukhrat Adkhamovich, ²Rakhimberdiev Oybek Alisher, ³Nasriddinov Dilshod
Azamkulovich**

¹NIU Department of international relations and organization of overseas trips

²NIU Head of the Department of Academic Affairs

³NIU Head of the Department of Foreign Languages, dilshodnasr@gmail.com

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***Abstract.** This article highlights the introduction of the successful experience of Finland in the development of the education system of Uzbekistan and also gives a brief history of the Finnish phenomenon. Uniform opportunities for all to study and receive high-quality education is one of the basic principles of the Finnish educational system. In Finland, it is believed that the educational environment should motivate innovation, create a space for creativity, and give everyone the opportunity to "shine".*

***Keywords:** Finnish model, knowledge, skills, method, technology, learning process, pedagogical research.*

In order to succeed, we must first believe that we can
(Nikos Kazantzakis).

Introduction

To date, the rich experience of Finland is being introduced into our university. We hope that in the future we will see effective results of Uzbek-Finnish cooperation. Many developing countries consider it a priority to introduce the Finnish model into their education system. Our President has spoken several times about the Finnish model and Nordic International University has implemented several significant tasks in this direction. To date, a certain experience has been formed at the Nordic University.

The University started its activity with 8 directions. With an increase in the need for higher education and professional areas, the bachelor's degree program has reached 12 and ATC has also reached 6 master's degree programs. At the same time, a doctoral program was opened after higher education. In addition, the "Work and travel" program is comprehensively effective and useful for students. If you ask what are the advantages of the Finnish model, then the teachers will answer you. So let's briefly consider what the Finnish model of education is.

The Main Part

For 100 years, Finland's educational system has been continuously developing and is now entering a new stage.

Every next generation received a better education than the previous one. The Finnish education system has been recognized all over the world. The international program for the assessment of educational achievements of students in the OECD (Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development) member countries known as the PISA Study (Program for International Student Assessment, PISA) – a test evaluating the functional literacy of schoolchildren in different countries of the world and the ability to apply knowledge in practice. It takes place every three years)), and the skills of Finnish schoolchildren often have a high rating.

In Finland, the attitude towards education is positive and education is valued.

100 years of Finnish education

Let’s look at the general education school in order, the first and main step to knowledge. For children to study well, they must eat high-calorie meals in this regard, there is such a thing as a free lunch in Finnish schools.

Today, all preschoolers, and elementary and high school students receive free meals on each of the five school days of the week. One of the secrets to the success of the Finnish school system is the school lunch. In 1948, the School Nutrition Act was passed, which obliged municipalities to provide schools with free lunches on each of the six school days. The food is healthy and delicious. In Finnish schools, grades were given on a scale from 4 to 10, and the highest score was 10. Students' academic performance was assessed twice a year. In recent years, the grading system has changed from a digital scale to letters.

Flexible learning. Stories show that the school system has been constantly updated for a hundred years. In recent years, among other things, in-depth study of various subjects based on phenomena has been introduced in schools. There are no more blackboards or chalk in the classrooms. A digital camera is installed on the teacher's desk in the classroom to display materials on an interactive whiteboard. The teacher can also show videos from his computer. Sometimes students use tablets or computers. Most of the training materials are already electronic.

Why do Finnish schoolchildren do less homework, but achieve great success?

Why is it that Finnish youth spend less time at school, and do less homework, but in the end achieve almost the best results in the world?

Many parents, concerned about the huge burden on children at school, would like to know the answer to this question. They begin to think about the expediency of large amounts of homework that they have to do with their children because Finnish schoolchildren do an excellent job without causing any inconvenience to their moms and dads. The OECD believes that "the most surprising thing about Finnish schools is that their students have fewer hours in the school curriculum than any other OECD member state." Finnish schoolchildren finish the school year earlier, study less, and the result is better.

Respect for teachers.

Children have less homework when compared with the UK, and a tutor in Finland is quite rare.

The key concept of the Finnish educational system is trust. Parents believe that the school knows how to make the right decisions, and how to provide a decent level of education, and schools, in turn, trust teachers. Teaching here is considered a prestigious job, and teachers correspond to their high status.

Also, the Finnish school system is inseparable from the culture it serves.

It is a cohesive, fair, and efficient society, and it has a permanent, reliable school system corresponding to it.

And it is worth mentioning that the situation in Finland has not always been like this. Their education is built on the foundation of reforms initiated in the 1970s and 1980s, which turned the regular school system into a leading one worldwide. Another success factor of the Finnish school is that extra hours are directly related to better results. It's about homework. Studies show that homework has a significant positive impact on school success. A study by the Department of Education found that students who did two to three hours of homework a day were almost 10 times more likely to pass exams than those who did not do homework. Finland differs significantly from

other countries in that teachers, schools, and municipalities can decide for themselves what and how to teach.

The new way of teaching and learning may lower Finland's ranking in the international Pisa program, but Finns are not interested in this. The most important goal is to develop skills in children that will be useful to them in the future.

Statement 1: Students will no longer be taught in classrooms. Teaching is based on the study of natural phenomena and everyday life, for which the teacher constantly walks with students on the street, conducting "experiments". "Studying phenomena is just one way of learning. It is important to use a variety of pedagogical techniques. Teachers become guides, help each child find their way of learning."

In Finland, unlike countries such as the United Kingdom and the United States, they do not believe that there are important and less important subjects. They all play an equally important role. The goal is to give young people a broad education, not to force them to learn one subject.

The teacher is always responsible for the students. The world is changing, and schools and education must change with it.

Many Finnish teenagers dream of becoming teachers, so there is fierce competition between those entering the pedagogical faculty. According to the new curriculum, the teacher becomes an "assistant" who will not only transfer knowledge to students but also guide them, helping them to learn about the world.

Finland's PISA ranking is not significant in the Finnish mind. This is akin to measuring blood pressure, which sometimes allows us to think about where we are going, but is not the focus of attention. Decisions related to training are not made based on PISA results. Instead, the essential factor is the knowledge that children and adolescents will need in the future.

Conclusion

1. Compulsory schooling begins at the age of 7 and ends at the age of 17. In addition, all children have the right to preschool education, lasting one year.

2. Education, textbooks, school supplies, and teaching materials are free in primary school (grades 1-9).

3. Students are offered free school meals every day

4. For first-graders and second-graders, the school day lasts a maximum of five hours, for high school students - seven hours. Each lesson lasts 45 minutes.

5. There are no nationwide exams or tests in Finland.

6. In total, the Finnish academic year has 190 school days. The academic year begins in mid-August and ends at the end of May. In addition to the summer holidays, which last 10 weeks, schoolchildren rest in the fall, at Christmas, and usually in February.

7. In Finland, almost all teenagers (99.7%) master the curriculum and graduate from secondary school.

8. Teachers from 1st to 6th grades are Masters of pedagogy. Teachers of grades 7-9 have a master's degree in the academic discipline they teach and are also highly qualified specialists in the field of education.

9. Pedagogical educational institutions are popular, so it is difficult to enroll there. For example, in 2014, only 9% of those who passed the entrance exam to the Faculty of Education were admitted to the University of Helsinki. As you know, today Finland is the absolute leader

among 193 countries in achieving 17 goals selected as indicators of sustainable development by the United Nations.

We hope that in the future, through our cooperation in the field of education, funded by the Government of Finland, we will implement all plans, in particular in the training of teachers in higher education, the improvement of curricula, and textbooks, the involvement of experienced specialists in these processes, the development of vocational education.

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